

A preliminary study on soft tooling process chain for injection moulding of a micromixer

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Abstract

The most expensive component of polymer injection moulded part is the mould since it requires specialized micromanufacturing technologies to machine intricate microfeatures in a hard to machine materials, such as tool steel. In the recent decade, we are witnessing fast growth of the implementation of additive manufacturing (AM) technologies into the manufacturing processes. Stereolithography (SLA) is an AM technique able to produce microfeatured parts from thermosets. Thus, it can be used to produce micro tool inserts which are characterized by the term soft-tooling. In this paper, we demonstrate a soft tooling approach to injection moulding, where the insert is made using low-cost SLA LCD 3D printer and resin. The polymer part geometry corresponds to a slanted groove micromixer. Two sets of injection moulding parameters were investigated and the insert wear and polymer parts geometry were dimensionally characterized throughout 50 injection cycles.

Keywords: soft tooling, injection moulding, micromixer, stereolithography, process chain, additive manufacturing.

1. Introduction

Miniaturization is a recent trend in analytical chemistry and life sciences as well as in non-silicon micromachining technologies [1],[2]. In the past two decades, the miniaturization of fluid handling and fluid analysis has emerged in the interdisciplinary field of microfluidics. Microfluidics is utilized in many natural science fields such as biochemistry analysis, chemical synthesis and medical diagnostics. The examples of microfluidics versatile applications stem from flow cytometry, sample injection in mass spectrometry, microreactor systems, PCR amplification, DNA analysis, separation and manipulation of cells, and many more. Due to said multi-purpose usage the designs of microfluidic devices differ vastly.

Manufacturing of polymer microfluidic components is a key technology for the implementation of microfluidic devices in consumer products [3]. When microfluidic chips will be produced in an effective, accurate and economical way, a whole range of new applications will emerge and the applications already existing will attract much more attention. Low-cost mass production of polymer microfluidic components can be achieved using either injection moulding or hot embossing. Both techniques require a tool to transfer the microstructures to the polymer material.

Injection moulding is a widely used manufacturing process for the production of high-quality plastic parts. Soft tooling is a subdivision of rapid tooling techniques that are used in injection moulding to create a less expensive and less durable mould than in traditional tooling. One of the earliest attempts on soft tooling using stereolithography (SLA) was by testing different simple prismatic features with varying dimensions and including conformal cooling channels [4]. The approach has gained significant attention in recent years due to its cost-effectiveness and efficiency since it effectively addresses the need for low volume cost-effective manufacturing of polymer parts e.g. testing and validation purposes, and reducing lead times for production, ultimately speeding up the time-to-market for new products.

SLA is a liquid-based AM process, from which 3D parts are made by curing a photosensitive polymer kept in a vat, thus the term vat photopolymerization process is often used. Various light sources are used for photopolymerization, namely gamma rays, X-rays, electron beams, ultraviolet (UV) and visible light source [5]. Controlled light irradiation induces a curing reaction, forming a highly cross-linked polymer. The light source is usually a laser beam, but recently digital light processing (DLP) projectors are used to cure the whole layer at the same time reaching resolutions down to 2 μm .

The process chain combining SLA to manufacture tool inserts for injection moulding successfully addresses the challenges related to tools for manufacturing paper bottles. Namely, the tool should be able to effectively flush out water from the pulp suspension during the moulding process, hence it needs to possess a large number of micro-features with a high aspect ratio [6]. Conventional sintered (porous) tools in the moulding process give rise to clogging of the channels inside the mould. Hence, a soft tooling process chain as an alternative to the sintered tools utilized in the moulding process was implemented and characterised [7]. Results confirm a better performance of soft tools over sintered ones.

But the process chain of SLA and injection moulding is mostly used to perform small-batch production of small parts, hence microfluidics greatly embraced the AM technologies. The attraction stems from two aspects of AM technologies [8]. The first aspect relates to the ability to produce truly three-dimensional features. The second aspect relates to the ability to rapidly realize a 3D microfluidic device from a constructed 3D model.

When high-flow polypropylene was injection moulded into acrylic-epoxy formulation (HTM 140 V3) to produce microchannels 100 μm wide and height from 25 μm to 100 μm , a maximum lifetime of soft tool inserts was 78 moulding cycles [9]. The low thermal conductivity of the plastic hinders the heat flow from the part to the mould. This leads to a high thermal load for the microstructures, which fail after repeated cycling. Similar results were obtained when a proprietary methyl methacrylate and acrylamide

monomer/oligomer blend photo initiated by a titanium dioxide-based photoinitiator was used for tool insert and Polyethylene (PE Purell 1840) as injected material was used [10].

The effects of thermal ageing on the behaviour of the mould inserts were examined [11]. Thermal ageing leads to crack formations making the most affected areas in the mould inserts. Thermal stress in the moulds can be decreased by increasing cooling time, but it leads to longer cycle time and decreased productivity. The cracks propagated much faster in the aged mould inserts and a lower number of shots were reached (the maximum and minimum number of cycles were 50 and 8 respectively). Moreover, higher surface roughness in the aged mould inserts is observed.

An assortment of photopolymers and stereolithography processes to produce 3D-printed moulds and polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) castings of micromixing devices was characterised regarding demoulding, dimensional and surface metrology and all of them were identified as a viable option for developing complex micromixing devices [12].

In this paper, a soft-tooling approach by producing the tool insert with a low-cost SLA LCD 3D printer and using low-cost resin is presented. Microfeature insert geometry resembles slanted groove micromixer design which is a popular micromixer geometry which efficiently mixes fluids on a microscale.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Inserts fabrication by additive manufacturing

The tool inserts were fabricated using Elegoo Mars 3 desktop LCD SLA 3D printer. This is a low-cost 3D printer with a declared pixel resolution in XY-plane (the build plane) of 35 μm . The photopolymer resin used was Phrozen Aqua 4K 3D Printing Resin, chosen for its low price, low shrinkage and good spatial resolution. After curing the resin has declared properties of surface hardness of 80 Shore D, tensile modulus of 1037 MPa, heat deflection temperature of 70° and ultimate tensile strength of 24 MPa. The printing parameters used were derived from the producer's recommendations and adjusted with respect to the test prints of tool inserts. Citubox slicer software was used. The final parameters used were the following: bottom exposure time of 30 s (for first 5 layers), regular exposure time of 2.4 s and a layer height of 50 μm .

The overall size of the tool insert was 20x20x2 mm with five slanted groove micromixer features ranging from bigger to smaller versions. For this study only the second largest was analysed, as depicted in Fig. 1. The nominal dimensions of said design were the following: protrusion height $d = 0.25$ mm, protrusion width $a = 0.5$ mm, channel protrusion height of 0.1 mm and channel protrusion width of 0.8 mm. For the purpose of this investigations two tool-inserts were produced, one for each injection moulding run. Dimensional standard deviation for protrusion heights was measured to be ± 11 μm and for protrusion widths ± 14 μm .

2.2. Injection moulding

Injection moulding tests were done on a

Cronoplast BABYPLAST 6/10P fully hydraulic, injection moulding machine equipped with a 10 mm injection piston diameter.

Polypropylene (PP) homopolymer (Borealis HF700SA) was used as the material for injection moulding mainly due to its moderate processing temperature, resistance to corrosion and chemical leaching.

Fig. 1. Above) Depiction of 3D model of the SLA tool insert with the denotation of protrusion dimensions. Below) 3D micrographs of tool inserts before injection moulding.

Fig. 2 illustrates how the tool insert was mounted into the injection half of the mould. The tool insert was pressed against the mould using a holding plate and four screws. The mould runner system was comprised of a conically shaped sprue, a semi-circularly shaped runner and a fan gate leading into the tool cavity.

Fig. 2. 3D model of the mould used in this study

Two sets (A and B) of injection moulding processing parameters were investigated denoted in table 1.

Table 1. Injection moulding parameter sets. Only injection speed parameter varied on two levels.

Setting	T _{mold} [°C]	Hydraulic pressure [bar]	Injection speed [mm/s]
A	15	20	22
B	15	20	44

The polymer melt temperature was fixed for both parameter sets at 170°C at the plastification unit, 175°C at the injection cylinder and 185°C at the

injection nozzle. The injection melt temperature was kept at the lower value of the processing recommendation for the PP so that the SLA printed tool insert was less thermally stressed. Likewise, the mould temperature was kept at 15°C with a tempering unit. By same reasoning, the pressure was kept at a low value of 20 bars of machine's hydraulic pressure to avoid cracking the polymer tool insert. Hydraulic pressure of 20 bar translates to 40 MPa of injection pressure when using $\Phi 10$ mm injection piston. This pressure is close to the lower bound of recommended injection pressures for PP, which is ~ 50 MPa. The only varied parameter was injection speed which was set to lower setting of 22 mm/s for parameter set A and to higher setting of 44 mm/s for parameter set B.

For each set of injection moulding runs a new insert was used. Each run lasted for 50 cycles. After a test run of 110 cycles, no cracks were observed on the core part of the tool insert. However, the occasional protrusion feature broke off after 40 cycles or more.

2.3. Dimensional measurements and characterisation

The microfeatures, i.e. protrusions, on the insert and microfeatures on the polymer part, i.e. grooves, were measured on a Keyence VHX-6000 digital microscope. The 3D surface was acquired using the depth composition function with a magnification factor of 100 and resolution of 2 μm in XY-plane. The first three microfeatures closest to the injection gate and the last three, thus, the furthest away were measured. The protrusion height on the insert and corresponding groove depth on the polymer part is denoted as d . Similarly, the protrusion width and groove width are denoted as a .

On the insert the microprotrusions were measured before and after the injection moulding runs. The injection moulded PP parts were grouped in batches of 10 pieces and microgrooves on the specimens were measured on the moulded parts at the cycle number 20, 30 and 40. Corresponding polymer parts are denoted as A20, A30 and A40 when injection moulding parameters A were set and B20, B30 and B40 when injection moulding parameters B were set. The average and standard deviation values of particular dimensions were calculated from all six microfeatures.

3. Results and discussion

The first observation was, the dimensional accuracy of the protrusions on the printed tool inserts were within the boundaries of the specified resolution of the used SLA LCD 3D printer. The mean value and standard deviation of measured heights of the protrusions were $253 \pm 9 \mu\text{m}$ and widths $506 \pm 15 \mu\text{m}$ which is in good correspondence with the printer's resolution.

3.1. Analysis of results for injection moulding setting A

The comparison from analysing the protrusion dimensions on the insert before and after injection moulding is depicted in Fig. 3.

It can be noted that protrusion height is lower after 50 injection moulding cycles for 38 μm . This signalizes that the top of protrusions were subjected to significant wear due to the inflow of polymer melt. The cause of wear is probably shear stress exerted on the

protrusions due to polymer melt flow. With respect to protrusion widths no significant wear was observed.

Fig. 3. Mean and standard deviation values of protrusions dimensions before (blue) and after (orange) the usage of the tool insert A.

After the 50 injection moulding cycles a torn-off protrusion was noticed at the position furthest away from the gate position (see Fig. 4). Plausible explanation for this might be that a crack appeared at the bottom of the protrusion at the demoulding stage. Namely, at the beginning of mould opening phase the part is pulled from the injection half of the mold by the sprue puller. At that instance it was noticed, that the polymer baseplate got slightly stuck in the mould cavity, causing a jerk of the plastic part in the direction towards the sprue causing some lateral pulling force at the protrusions furthest away from the gate. In subsequence cycles the melt pressure increased the crack and then finally it was ripped off during the demoulding phase.

Fig. 4. 3D micrograph of the three protrusions furthest away from the gate position (insert A).

The analysis of dimensions on the polymer part shows that the average value of groove depth stayed relatively constant after the 20th injection moulding cycle at $213 \pm 9 \mu\text{m}$ (see Fig. 5 and Fig.6). This implies that the main wear of protrusion height on the insert occurred before the 20th cycle. However, it is also plausible that groove depths are generally lower than the protrusion heights due to relatively low injection pressure being unable to reduce the polymer shrinking effect in the cooling stage.

The groove widths also didn't change significantly after 40 cycles with a mean value of $496 \pm 12 \mu\text{m}$. This is consistent with the absence of lateral wear on the tool insert protrusions.

Fig. 5. Left) Comparison of 3D micrographs for injection moulding run A, cycles 20 and 40. Right) Injection moulding run B cycles 20 and 40.

Fig. 6. Mean and standard deviation values of groove depths after 20, 30 and 40th cycle. Protrusions heights on insert A before moulding are depicted on the left for comparison.

3.2. Analysis of results for injection moulding setting B

Similar findings to insert microfeature wear at injection moulding setting A can be observed for setting B (see Fig. 7). Namely, wear occurred regarding the protrusion height d but was insignificant for protrusion width a . However, the wear regarding protrusion height was less significant, measured to be 15 μm .

Fig. 7. Mean and standard deviation values of protrusions dimensions before (blue) and after (orange) the usage of the tool insert B.

With respect to the integrity of the tool insert B it was observed, that the protrusion furthest away from the gate was torn off before cycle number 40 and by cycle number 50, the second to last protrusion got torn off too (see Fig. 8). This signifies that higher injection speed used in parameter set B exerts more load on the protrusions as it passes by and thus accelerates the occurrence of microcracks which can result in protrusion being torn off at the demoulding phase. By this observation we conclude that lower injection speed is a favourable setting when using SLA-printed tool inserts.

Fig. 8. 3D micrograph of the three protrusions furthest away from the gate position (insert B).

Dimensional analysis of groove depths on the polymer parts reveals, that the protrusion height wear occurred gradually over the moulding cycles (see Fig. 9).

Fig. 9. Mean and standard deviation values of groove depths after 20, 30 and 40th cycle. Protrusions heights on insert B before moulding are depicted on the left for comparison.

The groove widths didn't change significantly after 40 cycles with a mean value of $522 \pm 9 \mu\text{m}$. This is consistent with the absence of lateral wear on the tool insert protrusions.

4. Conclusions

In this study, a moderately successful use of the soft-tooling approach for injection moulding is presented. The SLA tool insert was produced using a low-cost SLA LCD printer and low-cost resin.

For the studied microfeature geometry the insert remained structurally stable until the 40th cycle using parameter set A and until the 30th cycle when using parameter set B. After mentioned cycles, the protrusion furthest away from the injection gate got torn off.

Since the replication degree of the protrusions was similar between both parameter sets we conclude, that the lower injection speed setting (set A) is favourable since it preserves the integrity of the tool insert for more injection cycles.

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